

Isolation of 3, 3'-Di-*O*-Methyl Ellagic Acid from *Sapium baccatum* Roxb. and *Sapium eugeniaefolium* Ham.

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The yellow benzene insoluble solid that separated out during benzene extraction of *S. baccatum* Roxb.¹ and *S. eugeniaefolium* Ham² has been identified as 3, 3'-di-*o*-methyl ellagic acid.

The solids collected by filtration of the benzene extract after repeated crystallisation from dimethylformamide afforded fine yellow crystals m.p. 322-24°, molecular ion peak at *m/e* 330 (mass), which corresponds to mol. formula C₁₆H₁₀O₈ (Found : C, 58.40; H, 3.59; —OCH₃, 18.02, Calc. for C₁₆H₁₀O₈ : C, 58.20; H, 3.0; 2-OCH₃, 18.8%), U.V. $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}}$ 250, 270 *mμ*, no shift was observed in U.V. spectrum with 0.1*M* sodium acetate solution, I.R. ν_{\max} 3300 (—OH), 1722 (carbonyl), 1610, 1590 (aromatic C-H) cm⁻¹. The solid was found to be sparingly soluble in usual organic solvents but readily dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution which on acidification with dil. HCl gave back the original compound. Methylation of the solid by refluxing with dimethyl sulphate and anhydrous potassium carbonate in acetone gave a solid which after crystallisation from dioxan-methanol gave needle shaped crystals m.p. 338-40°, (Found: C, 60.11; H, 4.05; —OCH₃, 31.7; Calc. for C₁₈H₁₄O₈ : C, 60.33; H, 3.96; 4-OCH₃, 34.63%), which was identified as tetra-*o*-methyl ellagic acid (III) (Lit.⁶ m.p. 340-41°) by comparison with an authentic sample (m.m.p and I.R. comparison). Acetylation of the solid either by refluxing with anhydrous sodium acetate in acetic anhydride or with pyridine-acetic anhydride gave the same compound of m.p. 300-2° and this has been identified as 3, 3'-di-*o*-methyl-4, 4'-diacetate (IV) of ellagic acid C₂₀H₁₄O₁₀. (Found : C, 58.01; H, 3.36; —OCH₃, 14.2; Calc. for C₂₀H₁₄O₁₀ : C, 57.95; H, 3.41; 2-OCH₃, 15.1%). This fact establishes that the compound m.p. 322-24° obtained from the bark of both the plants is 3, 3'-di-*o*-methyl ellagic acid (II), which has been found to be identical with an authentic sample³ of 3, 3'-di-*o*-methyl ellagic acid (m.m.p and I.R. comparison).

The compound (II) gave a light brown coloration with ferric chloride solution. It is reported that synthetic 3, 3'-di-*o*-methyl ether⁴ of ellagic acid does not give a positive ferric chloride coloration^{5,6,7}. The probable reason put forward for this is that the partial

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methyl ethers of ellagic acid may frequently occur along with the ellagic acid itself,⁷ the purification of which is difficult⁸. In this connection it is necessary to mention that we failed to isolate pure ellagic acid in the plant.

I, $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = R_4 = H$

II, $R_1 = R_3 = Me; R_2 = R_4 = H$

III, $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = R_4 = Me$

IV, $R_1 = R_3 = Me, R_2 = R_4 = -COCH_3$

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